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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tadbirkorlik psixologiyasining xususiyatlari va tadbirkorlik faoliyatining ijtimoiy-psixologik jihatlarini, yangi O'zbekiston yoshlari hayotida tadbirkorlik faoliyatining tutgan o'rni haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Tadbirkorlik, biznes, tashkilotchi, rag'bat, mehnat madaniyati, ishlab chiqarish tashkilotchisi, foyda.

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ ПОДХОД К ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация об особенностях психологии предпринимательства и социально-психологических аспектах предпринимательской деятельности, о роли предпринимательской деятельности в жизни молодежи Нового Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: предпринимательство, бизнес, организатор, стимул, культура труда, организатор производства, прибыль.

PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACH TO ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY

Annotation: this article provides information on the peculiarities of entrepreneurial psychology and socio-psychological aspects of entrepreneurial activity, the role of entrepreneurial activity in the life of young people of new Uzbekistan.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, business, organizer, incentive, labor culture, production organizer, profit.

In the conditions of modernization of the economy and further deepening of market reforms, the importance of business entities is important in ensuring the general employment of the population, increasing the income of the population and ensuring the sustainable development of the country. Because since the entrepreneur puts his funds into the sphere of production, at the same time, in addition to increasing his income, the society creates a material basis for the provision of other members with work and income.

Entrepreneurship, as a socio-psychological phenomenon, arouses the active interest of many foreign and domestic researchers, since one of its most important social functions is to improve the well-being of society. After experimenting with the state-bureaucratic economy for many years, our society adopts a long-recognized position in the world about the fact that the main mechanism for the development and renewal of economic life is the initiative and activities of a private entrepreneur.

When we talk about an entrepreneur, we first mean a producer entrepreneur, a "production organizer". At this point, a question arises in the minds of all young people, how to start an entrepreneurial activity. What positive qualities should be formed in the personality of the entrepreneur himself. Firstly, the desire to strive for independent and creative activities is inappropriate as a leading motive, and secondly, the desire to get rich quickly and easily.

One of the incentives for the development of entrepreneurial activity is often situational situations that affect the fate of people, encouraging them to solve their life problems by entering the path of entrepreneurship. Special abilities are necessary for this type of activity. A natural condition for the development of abilities is the presence of inclinations, some innate anatomical and physiological features of the brain and nervous system. Psychologist scientist V.A.Krutetskiy to krutetsky's position, the predisposition includes typological features of the nervous system, natural features of analyzers, individual variants of the cerebral cortex.

Despite the fact that entrepreneurship currently exists as an activity in every country of the world, the profession of "entrepreneur" does not exist. A common opinion among entrepreneurial researchers is that it is almost impossible to teach it. When people start a business, the knowledge gained in the process of simple study turns out to be almost useless, there is no connection between the business qualities of an entrepreneur and his education. By the way, Meyers – Briggs people who have an entrepreneurial personality under their special test are admitted to Harvard Business School. It is necessary to determine which inclinations contribute to the manifestation of entrepreneurial abilities, so that from early childhood a unique opportunity arises to identify those who are prone to entrepreneurship.

Both views of the entrepreneurial function in society are fair. Because this is a sequential change in functions that contribute to the development of an economy that disrupts the balance, and this is a powerful factor in development, since it does not allow the economy to stagnate or become unbalanced. These functions are the sides of one coin – a market environment in which an entrepreneur is formed as a person. Each of the functions fulfills its purpose at the appropriate stage of the development of entrepreneurial activity. The first is to create a market for new products. Here, entrepreneurial ability and data dominance are necessary to find unsatisfactory or potential consumer demand.

The second stage of entrepreneurial activity occurs when a new product is needed for the consumer. This stage is associated only with organizational aspects: expanding the volume of production, hiring new people, etc.

The main task of an entrepreneur is to unite all personal employees around him, to direct his efforts to achieve their goals. To do this, the head of the company must be able to immerse all hired workers in the environment of their value, which leads to the birth of a special culture of the organization. At this stage, entrepreneurship presents the "social architecture" - the study and creation of the "culture of labor" - at the same time intangible and difficult to identify elements that are very important: behavior, values and norms.

Thus, the main task of entrepreneurial activity is to bring the social economy from an unbalanced state to a state of equilibrium and to develop the economic environment in rapid pictures.

Conclusion

Any human activity, including entrepreneurial activity, has a certain structure. It includes goals-future results, activities aimed at achieving them; motives that stimulate activity; a topic that can be changed to achieve the goal, knowledge about this topic, methods and means of achieving the goal, as well as conditions of activity.

As a primary goal, the specifics of profit-seeking entrepreneurship depend on characteristics such as independence, responsibility, uncertainty, risk, creativity, innovation and initiative.

Entrepreneurship is the innovative activity of people belonging to a special social group called entrepreneurs who have unique abilities that allow them to develop not only the peculiarities of this activity, but also the economy of functions for profit.

Entrepreneurial behavior can be assumed to be related to the attitude that generates a state of readiness to carry out actions of an entrepreneurial nature, if there is a need and a situation that satisfies it.

List of literature used

1. Варфоломеева О. В. Fundamentals of psychology of activity: A textbook. – Simferopol: Tavria, 1999. – 180 с.
2. Мещерякова Е.В. Psychology of management: textbook. handbook. Mn.: Vysh. shk.,2005. – 237.
3. Реан А. А., Бордовская Н. В., Розум. С. И. Psychology and pedagogy. – St. Petersburg: Peter, 2000. – 432 с.
4. Роцин С. К. "Psychology of successful entrepreneurship in the USA". Psychological Journal.– 1993. Т.14 - №5.

5. Ф. Котлер. Fundamentals of marketing: trans. from English – 2nd European edition – М., 2000. – 944 с.
6. Чирикова А.Е. Psychological characteristics of an entrepreneur's personality. Psychological Journal. – 1990. Т. 19 - №1.

